

The Road to Kadengaan Cooperative: The Case of the Bugkalot Tribes in Nagtipunan, Quirino-Philippines

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Abstract

This study is aimed at assessing the extent of the Training Programs needed by the Bugkalot Tribe (indigenous people) in order to established a strong cooperative unhindered by limitations on the autonomy or organizational integrity of cooperatives. Data was gathered from the officers and members of the confederation of Bugkalot Tribe using a mixed techniques approach. Thematic content analysis and SPSS was used to analyze the data. Three variables were assessed: Extent of Bookkeeping and Financial Management training, Extent of Entrepreneurship and Business Management training, Records and office Management Training. The findings first demonstrate that the motivations of the respondents positively influence their involvement in the Training programs and the establishment of new businesses like the cooperative. Second, taking part in these programs has a positive impact on a person's entrepreneurial abilities and orientation.

Quirino State University is tasked with creating and implementing techno-transfer programs and modalities through efficient and productive training programs that will benefit the not only the Bugkalot Tribe but the entire community.

Additionally, this research aimed to advance a more comprehensive empirical understanding of how the various training programs will enable the indigenous people to establish the Kadengaan Agriculture Cooperative.

Keywords: *Techno-transfer programs, entrepreneurship, financial management, records management, cooperative.*

INTRODUCTION

In line with the Philippines' commitment to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the broad framework of the 2030 Agenda has several components that might help express the development concerns of indigenous peoples. Several of the SDGs and related aims are pertinent to indigenous peoples who are nearly always at a disadvantage compared to other groups of the population hence, the government needs to make sure that it contributes to achieving the collective aspirations of its citizens. The academe as one of the advisory committees were commissioned to identify strategic options for realizing the vision articulated by citizens. The goals and targets will stimulate actions which seeks to realize the human rights of all and to achieve gender equality to promote development-oriented policies that support productive activities, decent job creation, entrepreneurship, creativity and innovation, and encourage the formalization and growth of micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises, including through access to financial services.

(<https://www.globalgoals.org/goals/8-decent-work-and-economic-growth/>)

The Bugkalots are one of the prominent indigenous communities in Northern Luzon. The Bugkalots were known for being skilled headhunters, and this was seen as a part of their culture. The tribe holds a certificate of ancestral domain title (CADT), which they earned in 2016. A CADT is a title formally recognizing the rights of possession and ownership of indigenous peoples over their ancestral domains identified and delineated in accordance with Republic Act No. 8371 (Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act of 1997).

The idea was to establish a cooperative that would be owned and run by the tribe, since the Confederation of Bugkalot Quirino Chapter had just started running its own activities on various tourist attractions in the municipality of Nagtipunan.

Acknowledging the role that cooperatives play in a country's economic development, the establishment and expansion of cooperatives is a useful tool for encouraging self-sufficiency and utilizing the power of the people to achieve social justice and economic progress. According to the project's goals, Quirino State University will make sure that technical support and other services are provided to the aforementioned cooperatives so they can develop into sustainable businesses and, in turn, build a strong cooperative movement unhindered by limitations on the autonomy or organizational integrity of cooperatives. The Bugkalot Kadengaan Agriculture Cooperative was founded as a result of QSU's ability to offer pertinent trainings and technical support in the areas of bookkeeping, business management, entrepreneurship, financial management, office, and records management.

Going forward, the Quirino State University is dedicated to providing the necessary trainings to enhance the Bugkalot Kadengaan Agriculture Cooperative's operations, making it more productive, socially and environmentally conscious, and able to serve the larger community.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 outlines the Conceptual framework using the Independent and Dependent Variable Model.

Fig. 1: Paradigm of the Study

The Independent and Dependent Variable diagram illustrates the structure for the many initiatives envisioned to support the establishment of the Bugkalot Kadengaan Agriculture Cooperative.

The trainings and technical assistance offered by Quirino State University in the areas of bookkeeping, business management, entrepreneurship, financial management, office and records management make up the INDEPENDENT VARIABLE in this framework.

It began with the requirement to empower the participants, support the training process, keep an eye on activities, and assess the outcomes. These are all crucial in developing capacitaating a strong Cooperative which makes up the DEPENDENT VARIABLE.

The Confederation of Bugkalot and Quirino State University worked closely together to establish the Bugkalot Kadengaan Agriculture Cooperative as a result of their shared commitment to supporting extension services and answering the call for societal transformation.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in the Municipality of Nagtipunan, Quirino province where the Bugkalot Tribes lived for more than decades. They have been long recognized as one of the prominent indigenous people of the Northern Luzon.

The training programs are carried out through stages: needs assessment, implementation and evaluation. Data were collected base from the training needs assessment of the participants. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used to analyze the collected data, and the interviews were used to support and bolster the validity of the study's conclusions.

Officers and members of the Confederation of Bugkalot in Quirino province participated in this study. The survey questionnaire was used to collect pertinent data on the respondents' organizational profiles. The open ended questions were used to gather data on the following training programs: extent of Financial Management, Records and Office management, business and entrepreneurship. An in-depth interview was used to ask questions and generate discussions from the Bugkalot Tribe. This is done in an effort to increase the reliability of the data collected through human involvement. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethics guidelines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table1. Extent of Training on Bookkeeping and Financial Management

Benefits	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Financial management optimizes my capital structure	5	Strongly agree
Good financial management help me in forecasting my cash flows	5	Strongly agree
Good financial management help in mitigating financial risks	5	Strongly agree
Good financial management help us to make better decisions, plan finances well, and use resources wisely	5	Strongly agree
Good financial management help us make decisions that help our business grow and stay profitable	5	Strongly agree
Group Mean	5	Strongly agree

The training program's outcomes show that participants have a thorough understanding of the value and advantages of financial management, office and records management, business, and entrepreneurship as crucial components in the establishment of the Kadengaan Cooperative and the empowerment of its officers and members.

Financial management training is one of the most important training needs for employees in organization. It plays a crucial role in the management function of business start-ups sine it acts as a motivating factor in managing the finances of business. The officers asserted that they become more systematize and pro-constituent in approach to managing people and task. As one of the officers said that: ... *"The trainings we learned in preparing financial statements have been very helpful, especially since I am in the collection and cashier division..."* - collecting officer and cashier on tourist sites.

One of the participants also added that *"I am very grateful to QSU for responding to our request for technical assistance so that we can become a full-fledged cooperative, which we have long dreamed of...."*

According to a study conducted by the World Bank, successful project implementation is largely dependent on efficient finance management, especially in both government and non-government sector. Governments and organizations around the world stress the importance of prudent financial habits to guarantee the timely provision of services and the effective use of resources (World Bank, 2020).

Moreover, one of the key motivators for managing a company's finances is financial self-efficacy. Though little study has been done to ascertain if focused training enhances financial management abilities and financial self-efficacy, it is crucial for building financial management skills. (Kirsten, C. L. 2018)

In the Philippines, a study by (Garcia et al. 2020) examined the significance of financial management training to help employees of government and private sectors complete projects.

In addition, effective bookkeeping abilities are seen in financial literacy since it makes decision-making easier procedures include timely bill payment, appropriate debt control, etc. Bookkeeping act as guide when making inventory decisions hence leading to improved sales and profitability. (Chepkemoui et al. 2017)

Findings revealed that financial management is a key responsibility of all the personnel of the Kadengaan Cooperative, built on trust, partnership and accountability.

Table 2. Extent of Training on Business and Entrepreneurship

Benefits	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Develop a solid business plan and financial management skills	5	Strongly agree
Enhance leadership abilities, including effective communication and negotiation	4	agree
Build a robust network of mentors and industry experts	4	agree
Prepare for potential obstacles and develop resilience to overcome challenges	5	Strongly agree
Group Mean	4.5	Strongly agree

As a catalyst for industrialization and expansion, entrepreneurship is extremely important for promoting economic development. Joseph Schumpeter believed that a country's ability to innovate, which in turn depended on the distribution of entrepreneurial talent throughout its population, was inextricably linked to its economic development. Although technological developments are crucial, their conversion into economic growth depends on the entrepreneurial skills of those who can efficiently arrange and apply labor, capital, and technology. Experts stress that entrepreneurial activity is a necessary stimulant for economic development, which does not happen on its own due to favorable economic conditions alone. The presence of ambitious people is responsible for the abundance of activities observed in wealthy nations.

The above statement is in consonance with the statement of one of the participants... *"I now had an idea on how to run a cooperative, what are the requirements to start, and how to grow it..."*

Another participant also mentioned that ... *"I learned the importance of knowledge in business and entrepreneurship..."*

Those who possess this spirit of entrepreneurial leadership continue to lead the economic revolution that has proved time and again its ability to raise the standard of living for people everywhere. Scarborough, N. M., & Cornwall, J. R. (2019).

In addition to having a direct impact on business growth, entrepreneurial training also positively impacts business development and growth. (Indarti, S. 2021)

The entrepreneurship training program has improved the skills and abilities of its participants, increasing their independence and enabling them to launch new business. Galvão, A., Marques, C., & Ferreira, J. J. (2020)

This indicates that cultivating an entrepreneurial attitude is essential to forming future attitudinal biases. This promotes mindsets that concentrate on positive results and helps develop resilience (Ratten, V., & Jones, P. (2021).

Table 3. Extent of Training on Records and Office Management

Benefits	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
help organizations ensure compliance with regulatory requirements and industry standards	4	agree
Proper records management practices help to protect sensitive information from unauthorized access, loss, or theft	4	agree
help organizations streamline their workflows and improve decision-making	4	agree
Help increased productivity and reduced time spent searching for documents, ultimately saving the organization time and money	5	Strongly agree
Group Mean	4.25	Strongly agree

Legend:

4.21-5.00 *Strongly agree*
 3.41-4.20 *Agree*
 2.61-3.40 *Neutral/uncertain*
 1.81-2.60 *Disagree*
 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree*

Increased productivity and efficiency within the organization can also result from proper records management training. Workers can spend less time looking for information and more time finishing tasks if they are properly trained in file organization and management techniques, such as using a document management system. Increased productivity and, eventually, better overall performance for your company are possible outcomes of this.

Better record keeping might also result from records management training. Records can become more accurate and thorough if staff members are properly trained in record organization and maintenance. This can be particularly helpful in sectors like cooperatives where maintaining correct records is essential.

Some of the employees attested that through the technical assistance given to them they were able to get their salaries on time. As one of them states that: ... *"Because of the DTR and other office forms we made, we have a basis on how many hours and days our colleagues worked."*

"There has been transparency in all transactions at the tourism sites because the collectors assigned have up-to-date records..."

"A records management system results in a source of information about business activities that can support subsequent activities and business decisions, as well as ensuring accountability to present and future stakeholders," according to the 1996 Australian Standard AS 4390, Records Management (ISO 15489-1:2001).

In particular, it is believed that by avoiding or reducing the risks that often accompany it, irregularities that could hide cases of corruption will be easier to prevent the more records management is enhanced and incorporated into the daily operations of public and private institutions. De Mingo, A. C., & Cerrillo-i-Martínez, A. (2018). It is indeed including transparency obligations into a record's lifecycle prevents the occurrence of any corruption risk associated with the management.

The statement that "transparency requires records management systems that make it possible to control records" is made by Moyano. (Moyano Collado, 2015, 48).

In addition to providing resources and training for records management, cooperatives must establish legal frameworks for cooperative records keeping and educate their members on the importance of archival records. Iwata, J. J. (2023)

Thus, results showed that records and office management is of great importance in any organization since most businesses failed due to inadequate record keeping.

CONCLUSION

Training and development are crucial to an organization's efficacy and to enabling experienced workers to perform their jobs well & efficiently. Training is thought to have an impact on personal growth, work devotion, and productivity. Every corporate organization has to train and develop its employees. The majority of the organization is cognizant of this necessity and invest in and take part in a variety of training and development activities. Our staff members may receive technical training, training or behavioral/soft skills training. Additionally, it is stated that investing in training and development for businesses is typically seen as sound management practices and as a way to preserve the necessary level of knowledge in the sector, both now and in the future.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To increase the efficacy of training cooperatives must examine the training and development related to the specific task performed by an employee or personnel.

First, employees should have the motivation to acquire new skills and knowledge necessary to perform functionally. Because workers will be able to carry out their responsibilities and contribute significantly to the achievement of the organization's objectives.

Second, training should address workplace difficulties and foster a healthy culture about the management of human resources.

Finally, to stay competitive, cooperative employees must possess driven skills. Along with having committed and well-trained staff. The cooperative places a strong emphasis on having highly skilled and driven individuals.

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